

PITA CASE APPLICATION REPORT

HOME AUTOMATION SYSTEM (HOMESYS)

Executive summary

This report documents the application of a tree-based privacy threat modeling approach called PITA (Privacy Impact Tree Analysis) to the HomeSys application case. This is a home automation framework that supports the extensive automation of the home environment. HomeSys represents an open platform, providing application providers the ability to publish and deploy different applications, making them available to residential users to install based on their specific needs. Customers can customize the installation to meet their specific needs.

Part I provides detailed information about the application, its goals, technical background, and concretizes a number of application types.

Part I of the report provides a comprehensive description of the application case.

The application of the PITA approach is provided in Part II of this report and starts with the specification of a Data Flow Diagram (DFD). After that, the step-by-step application of the PITA framework is illustrated, leading to a number of knowledge structures: *Privacy impact trees*. Finally, a privacy footprint analysis is performed, aggregating the impact of the system as a whole.

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Part I

Case description

Home automation

Home automation is the residential extension of building automation. It is automation of the home, housework or household activity to provide improved convenience, comfort, energy efficiency and security. Home automation may include centralized control of lighting, HVAC (heating, ventilation and air conditioning), appliances, security locks of gates and doors and other systems. The popularity of home automation has been increasing greatly in recent years due to much higher affordability of hardware, and increased interconnectivity and simplicity via mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets. The concept of the “Internet of Things” (IoT) has tied in closely with the popularization of home automation.

Figure 1: High-level overview of a HomeSys installation.

Figure 1 provides a schematic overview of a typical home automation system. **Sensors** and **actuators** installed throughout the house relay data to an online system via a **Gateway**. The online services are accessible for the customer (end-user) via a tablet or a browser. The customer can both monitor his or her house as well as control the available actuators, for example dim the lights or turn up the heating. For certain alarming events (e.g., in case of a smoke) the user can get immediate notifications.

HomeSys

We focus on the design and development of a home automation gateway and its online services. The system is initially being built for the domestic market, focusing on remote monitoring and automation of residential apartments and houses. However, it would be beneficial if the same system can be easily extended for other purposes, e.g., monitoring of server centers, storage facilities, etc. Our target customers are people who would like to keep an eye on their apartment

or house, early adopters that are interested in smart systems and home automation.

HomeSys operates a service model. Customers will be able to define relatively straightforward rule-based applications leveraging their basic sensor/actuator information. Customers can subscribe to additional end-to-end application via an online store. These applications are more complex as they leverage various sensors and contain more complex logic. In our initial roll out to the market, we will offer a smart heating application that takes into account the inhabitants' routines, a light management application and a burglary detection application.

Technology stack

The HomeSys system consists of the following building blocks.

Mote is a hub into which the sensors and actuators are plugged.

Motes are powered either by a battery or they can be plugged into an electrical or light socket. Each mote has multiple ports where sensors and actuators can be physically plugged into.

Sensor is a hardware device that produces measurements and sends them to the gateway via a mote. The sensors are physically plugged into a mote.

Actuator is a hardware device that has one or more actions associated with it. For instance, a camera supports "take picture" and "take multiple pictures" actions, while a switch supports "turn on" and "turn off" actions. These actions are triggered by the gateway. The actuators are also plugged into the motes.

HomeSys gateway identification key is a USB-like peripheral that belongs to the HomeSys gateway. The identification key makes it possible to automatically configure a mote to connect to the HomeSys gateway to which the key belongs to (i.e., to make sure your motes do not connect to your neighbours' gateways).

HomeSys gateway is a pluggable "black-box" device installed in the end-user's home. The gateway relays the sensor data to the online system and manages the sensors and actuators. The gateway is a Linux platform running custom software developed in-house. This gateway hardware is sufficiently powerful to run a high-level execution environment (e.g., to run Java/Python programs) and a modern database management server (e.g., MySQL), but obviously has performance limitations. The gateway connects to the HomeSys online services via a wireless communication dongle.

HomeSys Online System is an online web portal to which our customers and end users can connect. After logging in, they can consult the information about their house or apartment, subscribe for additional services and buy new end-to-end smart-home applications.

As mentioned, sensors, actuators and motes are provided by third parties. The motes interface is compliant with the Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP). This is a RESTful protocol. The motes offer their peripherals (sensors and actuators) as CoAP resources that are available via GET/PUT/POST. The content returned back (e.g., a GET message on a temperature sensor) is typically encapsulated into a JSON message. The motes support the following events:

1. **Heartbeat.** Every mote periodically sends POST heartbeats to the gateway indicating it is alive.
2. **Data.** Motes either PUT/POST information from their sensors to the gateway (e.g., door is open, motion is detected, camera image) or information can be requested using GET (e.g., temperature and humidity readings). Furthermore, actuators can be controlled by sending POST requests (e.g., turn on/off a switch).
3. **Sensor plugged in.** Whenever a new sensor is inserted in the mote the mote sends a POST immediately to notify the gateway.
4. **Sensor removed.** The mote notifies the gateway by issuing a DELETE operation whenever a sensor is removed.

Overall System Goals

The main goal of the system is to provide the customers with appropriate tools to monitor their home and to get prompt notifications about critical events (e.g., smoke, low or high temperature, etc.).

In order to achieve the primary goals, HomeSys should realize (at least) the following goals.

- **Basic home monitoring and management.** All sensor data should be synchronized to the HomeSys Online system where the customers can consult all the information relevant to their home. Customers should also be able to manage their actuators as well as configure actuator actions depending on certain sensor value readings.
- **Smart home applications.** HomeSys should initially support three applications that customers can additionally purchase: (1) smart heating, (2) light management and (3) burglary detection.

- **Usability and user friendliness.** HomeSys should be completely plug-and-play, requiring minimal manual configuration and work out of the box.

The remainder of this section zooms in on each of these goals.

Basic home monitoring and management

The HomeSys gateway continually synchronizes its sensor data to the HomeSys Online system. It is essential that the synchronization protocol works correctly in the presence of non-reliable communication network. The 3G network could switch to Edge and that would mean that the synchronization protocol could more easily suffer from timeouts or network errors. While basic sensor data (e.g., temperature, humidity readings) can be packaged in relatively small units of transfer, image data coming from the camera could be large. All this monitoring data will be made available for the customers to consult at any time via the online services.

Customers obviously do not want to sit the whole day looking at a web page with their HomeSys monitoring information. Hence, we would like to allow the customers to easily create specific **events** of interest about which they would like to be notified. These events are triggered by specific sensor data values. Some examples of events that could be relevant to end users are: temperature measurements exceeding 35°C, motion detected at night, doors opened or closed, etc. To support this, we envision a basic rule-based system (condition-action rules), in which the end-user can define **rules**, in which the *conditions* are the events of interest and the *actions* can either be certain sensor-related actions (e.g. take a picture, turn off the heating), or issuing **notifications** or **alarms** which are sent to the end user¹.

As mentioned earlier, nodes also support actuators (e.g., buzzer, camera, on/off switch). Each actuator type supports a set of pre-defined actions/states. For instance, a buzzer has “on” and “off” actions, a camera has a “take picture” action. In addition to sending alarms or notifications, customers should also have the possibility to define basic rules that link events to actuator actions/states. For instance the event “motion is detected” could be linked to the camera “take picture” action, or “door open” could be linked to a light switch “on” action. All these rules are managed by the customer on the HomeSys Online system. Note that actuators may have a certain lag before their state changes. While some actuators are pretty much instant (e.g., buzzer on/off), others may require some time before they complete the action (e.g., camera shutter speed).

Finally, customers can also invoke **remote actuation commands** to

¹ The main reason of making such distinction is to allow the system to give priority to processing alarms over processing regular sensor data and notifications.

request certain actuator actions/states (e.g., take picture, start buzzer, turn on heating, etc.).

Smart home applications

In the basic home management scenario the customers can already create some minimalistic applications to control their house. However, some things cannot be implemented using the simple rule-based paradigm. Hence, for a certain subscription fee the customers can sign up for more sophisticated, fully automated and maintained solutions that are created with specific goal in mind. As mentioned earlier, we will initially focus on three applications, i.e., smart heating, light management and burglary detection.

In addition to these three applications we would like to allow both the HomeSys gateway as well as the online system system to be easily adaptable for new applications in the future (that could leverage new types of sensors). More information regarding the specifics of these applications is provided in Section I.

Usability and user-friendliness

Existing systems similar to HomeSys in many cases require extensive and complicated installation/configuration procedures, and as discussed before, we would like to promote on ease of installation and user-friendliness as one of the key selling points of our HomeSys solution.

Of relevance are the following considerations:

- As soon as the HomeSys gateway is plugged into the electrical socket, it immediately connects to the online system and starts sending data.
- As soon as a new mote is powered up, it is instantly recognized by the HomeSys.
- Sensors that are plugged in (or out) into the motes, should also appear instantly within the HomeSys.
- In degraded circumstances (e.g. limited or no 3G connectivity), the gateway should adapt itself without requiring user intervention.
- Power outages should not affect the ability of the gateway, the motes or sensors to continue normal operations when the power supply is restored.

From a technological point of view, these goals are feasible but require specific attention. For instance, a 3G module allows HomeSys

to require no configuration to get online. Motes broadcast information as soon as they are powered on. The broadcasted information contains both meta-information regarding the sensors that are available, as well as sensor data.

Installation should be as easy as registration and powering on or plugging in the devices.

Each HomeSys gateway and its motes do not interfere with other HomeSys environments. The protocol is encrypted and secure. This means that you don't have to worry about two neighbors each having a HomeSys gateway at home. In order to configure a mote to connect to a specific HomeSys gateway it is sufficient to simply plug in the HomeSys gateway identification key into the mote. The mote firmware automatically reconfigures the mote to only connect to the gateway corresponding to the identification key.

Sensors and Actuators

HomeSys works with a fixed set of sensors and actuators, i.e., temperature, humidity, smoke and CO₂, motion, open/closed doors and windows and actuators to turn on/off electrical circuits.

In general, there are two types of sensors, i.e., sensors that should be polled regularly to obtain the readings and sensors that will push data themselves when their state changes. The first category of sensors requires an explicit GET request towards the sensor to fetch a reading from the sensor. The second type of sensors will trigger an event whenever a new value (or a state change) is available. Such a triggered event is linked to what we refer to as callback. The callback is essentially a POST request to the gateway.

- **Temperature and humidity sensor.** This is a combined sensor that samples the environment temperature and humidity. The temperature reading has a range from -30°C to +85°C. The humidity reading has a range from 0–100% relative humidity.
- **Smoke and CO₂ sensor.** This is a sensor that triggers an event in case of smoke. Only when smoke or CO₂ is detected the sensor will spring alive. It will also report when the detection of smoke or CO₂ has stopped. It is possible to configure the sensitivity of this sensor. In the first version this is done using a hardware screw. However, in the future we expect to work with smoke sensors that will allow adjusting the sensitivity via the software (by sending configuration POST requests to the sensor).
- **Motion sensor.** This is a sensor that invokes a callback (POST request) when motion is detected and when detection ends. The

motion detector operates on the infrared frequency, thus light is not strictly necessary to detect motion. It is possible to configure the sensitivity settings of the motion sensor.

- **Light sensor (photosensor or photodetector).** This is a sensor that invokes a callback (POST request) periodically sending the current light level. The period can be configured using a POST configuration request to the sensor. Also the sensitivity of the light detection can be configured, i.e., what is an absolute light and no light.
- **Door/window sensor.** This is a sensor that invokes a callback (POST request) when the door/window opens or closes. The door/window sensor typically consists of two magnets and a wire running from one of the magnets all the way to the sensor plugged into the mote.
- **Camera actuator.** This is a camera that on request can take one or more pictures. The request to take pictures is not blocking. This means that the camera will invoke a POST request when the pictures are ready. The gateway should perform the coordination if multiple processes simultaneously request the same resource.
- **Buzzer actuator.** This is an actuator that takes two commands, i.e., start and stop the buzzer. The commands are POST requests to the sensor.
- **Switch actuator.** This is a generic actuator that can be hooked up to a variety of devices to turn them on and off. Commands are sent by the gateway as POST requests.

Table 1 provides an overview of all initially-supported sensors and actuators.

All resources have a unique network identifier (IPv6 address). The gateway will be capable of communicating directly to all sensors and actuators.

Home Applications

This section describes the three end-to-end applications that Home-Sys will initially support in addition to the basic home monitoring and home management facilities. These applications are configured via the online system.

It is outside the scope of this assignment to provide a detailed, algorithmic description of how each application works.

Sensor type	Comm.	Config.	Relevant technical details
Temperature and humidity	Polling	None	Temperature reading range from -30°C to $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$, Humidity reading range from 0–100%
Smoke and CO_2	Callback-based	Sensitivity calibration	Detecting range: 20ppm-2000ppm carbon monoxide
Motion	Callback-based	Adjustable sensitivity, adjustable delay before firing	Infrared over max. 6.5m
Light	Periodic callback	Callback period and sensitivity level	None
Door/window	Callback-based	None	Open/close values based on a magnetic sensor
Camera actuator	Request-response	Quality and resolution	Max. resolution of 2592×1944 pixels
Buzzer	Request-response	None	90 dB
On/off switch	Request-response	None	None

Table 1: Summary of sensor and actuator types.

Smart heating application

The heating application allows the customer to control the heating (and cooling systems) in his home in a semi-automated way. The heating application will control the heating system based on the temperature sensor readings, motion sensor, weather predictions as well as additional customer preferences. The heating application should support at least the following goals:

- A minimum temperature is always maintained independent of whether someone is at home or not.
- Whenever someone is at home, a comfort temperature level is maintained. This comfort level is configured by the customer via the online system.
- The daily routine of the inhabitants is learned to pre-heat the

home to a comfort level, for example, during the sleeping hours the temperature level is lowered. It is up to the system to figure out the sleeping hours based on motion sensors and light sensors.

- The customers can manually turn on/off the heating via the HomeSys Online System dashboard and override the default behavior.

The heating applications requires temperature sensor(s), motion sensor(s), light sensor(s), heating system on/off actuator, and in terms of online configuration by the end-user, the minimum and comfort temperature levels.

Light management application

The light management application will provide a very basic control of the home light based on time of the day, day light sensor, motion sensor and additional customer preferences. The light management application should support at least the following:

- If the light sensor detects that it is getting dark outside and motion is detected, the lights are switched on.
- The customer can modify the sensitivity settings based on the daylight illumination level.
- The customer can indicate that during the night certain light bulbs should always stay on (e.g., toilet lights, corridor lights).

The light management application requires motion sensor(s), light sensor(s), on/off switch(es), and relies on the house topology, and additional customer configuration, for example to set illumination levels.

Burglary detection application

The burglary detection application detects break-in attempts. Initially, a relatively simple version of the burglar application will be offered that requires the customers to arm and disarm the burglar system by, for example, pressing a button or via the mobile app. The burglary detection application should support at least the following goals:

- When a door or a window is opened, or when motion is detected in the house, the burglary detection application generates an initial alarm. The customer receives a soft warning and has one minute to disarm the system.
- If the system is not disarmed within that time period, the system sounds an alarm (via the buzzer) and sends alarm messages to the end-user.

- In addition, the application also triggers image capturing and sends this information to the customer to decide whether or not this is a false alarm.
- The customer can at all times stop the alarm remotely, and also arming or disarming can be done remotely, for example using the mobile app.

The burglary detection application requires motion sensor(s), door/window sensor(s), buzzer(s), and can be controlled via the website and the mobile app.

Online System and Services

In this section, we describe the online system and the various services that are offered by HomeSys.

- **Initial registration and login.** End users can register for HomeSys by providing their personal information and their e-mail address. After e-mail validation, their profile is completed with further information about installation address, invoicing address and other billing-related aspects. Once the registration is confirmed, the customer is sent a gateway device overnight. In the final step of customer registration, the customer is requested to enter the serial number of his gateway (which obviously is unique). Once the gateway device is installed and powered on, the customer can log in into the online system.
- **Webshop.** The HomeSys Online system provides a webshop where customers can order individual hardware elements (sensors, motes) as well as purchase software system subscriptions (which often come with additional hardware elements). The webshop features a third party payment integration. The webshop consists of two sub-stores:
 - Hardware store. In the hardware store, customers can simply order hardware elements, namely, motes, sensors and actuators. This part of the webshop is relatively simple and straightforward.
 - Application store. In the application store, customers can subscribe to a specific home application that, as mentioned earlier, has specific hardware requirements. In a first instance, HomeSys will offer the three applications as outlined in the previous section. When the customer wishes to subscribe a certain application, the application store must validate whether the customer already owns the required sensors and actuators. If not, the

webshop will automatically add these sensors to the customer's shopping cart. The actual activation of a home automation application is only done when the hardware prerequisites are available (i.e., when the new sensors have arrived, have been installed, powered on and recognized).

- All applications have a recurring (weekly or monthly) fee. Subscriptions are automatically suspended, which includes disabling all rules part of the application, when the user does not prolong them. However, the sensors/actuators keep on functioning and the user still gets raw sensor information. For example, when suspending the smart heating application the temperature data is still recorded as before but the system will no longer maintain a minimum temperature. The customer can at all times manually create his own rule-based applications.
- **HomeSys Dashboard.** Customers interact with the HomeSys system primarily via a dashboard providing them access to their sensor data and notifications and allowing them to edit and manage their rules. Immediately after registration, the HomeSys Dashboard is empty.
- **Topology configuration.** The online system allows the user to create a topology of the house/apartment and place the gateway, motes, sensors and actuators on a house plan. Some of the HomeSys applications will benefit from or even require more in-depth knowledge of the topology of the premise in which these hardware elements are installed, for example, e.g. to know which camera to activate to film potential burglars, i.e., one near the motion sensor that triggered the alarm, or mapping light intensity sensors and lights to rooms. Note that the sensors and the motes can be assumed to be physically in the same location. Certain sensors, such as door/window sensors, can be hooked up to the motes with a wire, but we assume that the wire is relatively short.
- **Data, notification & alarm overview.** The end-user can consult his raw sensor data via the online system. He can view various charts of the sensor readings over a specific period of time. In addition, he can look at current (and past) notifications and alarms.

HomeSys provides three different mechanisms for sending out notifications to the customers, i.e., e-mail, SMS and push notifications to the mobile app (see below).

HomeSys mobile app

To increase the usability of the HomeSys online platform we also want to offer a mobile app customers can install on their smartphone or tablet. This app will make a number of the above-mentioned functionalities more easily available for customers. For instance, the app is especially useful for alarms, notification and live actuation such as arming disarming the burglary alarm system.

Service Level Agreements

Our firm offers a Service Level Agreement (SLA) enclosed as a part of the provided support towards our customers. This agreement stipulates certain quality requirements (in terms of performance, availability, security and privacy). For example, there should be an upper limit in the time it takes for a notification to reach its recipient. Evidently the upper limit for alarm notifications should be much more strict than for normal notifications (e.g., 95% of alarm notifications should reach the recipient within 30 seconds, and 95% of event notifications should reach the recipient within 3 minutes).

Aside from the notification/alarm SLA our firm will also provide two different SLAs for customers. The free, basic subscription allows for the customers' gateway to periodically, i.e., once every 10 minutes, synchronize new sensor data to the HomeSys online system. Furthermore, a basic subscription will allow customers to access their data only for the past three months. When enrolling in the premium subscription, by paying a yearly fee, customers receive real-time access to their sensors via the HomeSys online system. Moreover, premium customers are able to access their data for the past three years. Customers can easily move from one SLA level to another. SLA information should be synchronized to the gateway as well. New end user services that we offer (e.g., automatic sprinkler services) might introduce additional constraints to these SLAs (for instance, data update interval guarantees).

Also, our company has to negotiate a number of service level agreements with several third parties: the telecom operator to ensure the desired degree of gateway connectivity.

Security

Considering the nature of the HomeSys system (sensor data should be protected by all means), it is obvious that security is key concern in the system. Security in itself is a very complex subject that affects many layers of the system, and it should therefore be considered very early in the development process. In a first instance, the scope

is limited to basic *user authentication* and *user authorization* at the HomeSys Online system.

User authentication. Authentication is the process of ensuring the identity of the different actors. It should not be possible for a user to act as another user (spoofing) and users should not be able to access the system without authenticating. The HomeSys Online system should support appropriate authentication mechanism (e.g., user name and password) in order to ensure a sufficient degree of security.

User authorization. The online system will provide customers access to their data. Clearly, the dashboard should ensure that only authorized users can access their own data, manage their own modules, etc. Authorization strongly relies on authentication.

Main stakeholders

This section provides an overview of the main stakeholders in our system and their points of interest.

- **Customers.** The customers' main stake in the system is that they would like to have a tool to monitor their home, define events of interest in a user-friendly fashion, get prompt notifications upon these events and link these events to specific actions. They would also like to easily extend their HomeSys installation with new sensors/actuators. In general, customers and end-users want a hassle-free experience.
- **Mote manufacturer.** The motes are hubs for plugging multiple sensors and actuators.
- **Sensor and actuator manufacturer.** The sensor and actuators are plugged into the motes in order to communicate with the gateway.
- **HomeSys system administrator.** The HomeSys system administrator or operator monitors the online system for its correct working. They are responsible for performance and scalability of the online system. They are notified in case of any alarming events about the IT infrastructure that supports HomeSys.
- **HomeSys developers.** The HomeSys developers continually work and improve upon the existing services, not just the mobile app and the HomeSys online platform, but also the smart home applications, by issuing bug fixes and releasing updates of existing applications, the gateway operating system and firmware. For them, upgrade and update should happen smoothly and in a fully automated fashion (transparent to the end-user).

- **Telecom operators.** Telecom operators provide means for the gateways to communicate with the online system and vice versa. A service level agreement between our company and the telecom operators determines the capabilities of these communication channels.
- **Server providers.** The server providers provide physical or virtual servers that will be used to deploy the HomeSys Online system services. A service level agreement between our company and the server providers determines the server uptime constraints as well as the reaction time in case of hardware problems.
- **Market researchers and statisticians.** Given that the HomeSys applications produce vast amounts of data, this data could be used in various types of market research and the generation of certain statistics. For instance, it might be of interest to know the average temperature in houses around the year. This data will be sold by our firm in an anonymized format.

Part II

PITA application

HomeSys Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

Through hardware devices called IoT Motes, it interacts with the Sensors and Actuators to respectively obtain values (e.g., obtain room temperature) and perform actions (e.g., turn on light) in a home environment. These interactions are governed by the HomeSys Gateway, a dedicated device installed in the user's home that runs HomeSys software together with dedicated HomeSys applications. This device synchronizes and interacts in turn with the HomeSys back-end which stores sensor data, keeps track of applications (subscriptions, updates, etc.), provides a means for the End user to interact with the platform or the applications and performs user management. Through the HomeSys back-end, the Application provider is provided with a means to deploy, update and debug the different home automation applications. As indicated in the trust boundary on the right, the actual storage of sensor data itself is outsourced to a Database-as-a-Service (DBaaS) provider such as Amazon DynamoDB.

Figure 2: HomeSys Data flow diagram (DFD).

The Data Flow Diagram (DFD) shown in Figure 2 presents the overall architectural overview of the HomeSys platform. This is the basis for the evaluation of privacy threats. Through hardware devices called **IoT Motes**, it interacts with the **Sensors** and **Actuators** to respectively obtain values (e.g., obtain room temperature) and perform actions (e.g., turn on light) in a home environment. These interactions are governed by the **HomeSys Gateway**, a dedicated device installed in the user's home that runs HomeSys software together with dedicated HomeSys applications. This device synchronizes and interacts in turn with the HomeSys back-end which stores sensor

data, keeps track of applications (subscriptions, updates, etc.), provides a means for the **End user** to interact with the platform or the applications and performs user management. Through the **HomeSys back-end**, the **Application provider** is provided with a means to deploy, update and debug the different home automation applications. As indicated in the trust boundary on the right, the actual storage of sensor data itself is outsourced to a **Database-as-a-Service (DBaaS) provider** such as Amazon DynamoDB.

We follow the steps of the PITA approach.

1. Elicitation phase.

1.1. Identify data subject types

The following data subjects may be involved in a HomeSys installation:

- **Application provider:** this is the application developer that deploys home automation applications and makes them available to HomeSys users.
- **HomeSys users (End User):** this is the data subject that deliberately installs and configures the HomeSys system in the physical environment (e.g. home user, building administrator).
- **Building users:** this is the data subject that takes part of the physical environment (incidental, or recurrent) but does not have control or perhaps awareness of HomeSys (e.g. visitors, employees, tenants, ...)
- **System administrator:** this a HomeSys employee, responsible for the operational context of the HomeSys platform.
- **DBaaS provider:** external cloud provider that provides storage services for persisting the collected data sets. This is a honest-but-curious actor.

1.2. Instantiate privacy impact tree roots

We identify and list the following possible negative privacy outcomes (privacy impact instances) of HomeSys. The Privacy Impact types that are instantiated by these examples have been underlined.

- **T1. Loss of anonymity of building users:** incidental building users (e.g. passers-by, or delivery workers) may want to remain anonymous. The services offered by HomeSys may negate that.

- *Extent of impact-score: **Medium*** (Homesys), identification may be desired (e.g. for burglary detection, access control, etc). Anonymity when entering shared spaces can not be expected entirely.
- **T2. Surveillance** of HomeSys users or building users: an operator or developer may actively follow-up on the activities of individual, singled-out users (e.g. by obtaining camera images).
 - *Extent of impact-score: **High*** (Homesys is installed in the personal space of the users)
- **T3. Inaccuracy** of collected data leads to HomeSys user misrepresentation: not guaranteeing accuracy may lead to negative outcomes (e.g. incorrect bill, incorrect profiles or classification of users, the user making wrong decisions (interference)).
 - *Extent of impact-score: **Medium*** (the data is mainly operational)
- **T4. Lack of proactive communication** towards Building users: Building users may not be aware of the data collection activities, as the system may not be well-communicated or -advertised; user remain unaware of its functions and consequences.
 - *Extent of impact-score: **High*** (unaware users lead to non-compliance)
- **T5. Loss of Self-determination**: The HomeSys user can not switch to another provider or system without incurring severe loss of data or functionality.
 - *Extent of impact-score: **Medium*** (this may be desired, privacy implications to lock-in here are low)
- **T6. Lack of intervention** when the system malfunctions: HomeSys could take impactful automated decisions (e.g. force a door or window to remain open) which cannot be overruled by its users.
 - *Extent of impact-score: **High*** (the user may lose a degree of self-governance or sovereignty or control of the physical environment to the system)
- **T7. Exclusion** of HomeSys user: HomeSys data collection leads to the potential exclusion of users (e.g through profiling) in other contexts (e.g. services).
 - *Extent of impact-score: **High*** (Leads to an unfairness/discrimination against or in favor the HomeSys users)

- **T8.** Loss of anonymity: DBaaS provider can identify HomeSys users or Building users in sensor data: the DBaaS provider may re-identify the user at the basis of unique, distinguishing properties visible in the data (e.g. sensor ID, location information, etc).
 - *Extent of impact-score*: **High** (This is a significant leak of personal data, with exploitation potential)
- **T9.** Comparative profiling of application providers: the platform may engage in extensively profiling the behaviors of the application developers, e.g. how frequently and quickly they follow-up on issues, feature requests, etc.
 - *Extent of impact-score*: **Low** (developer privacy is not a key target; they act in a professional context)
- **T10.** Interference due to malfunction: the system may actively hinder the day-to-day activities of the HomeSys or the Building user, due to malfunction or improper implementation.
 - *Extent of impact-score*: **Low** (this is limited to interference in environment, does not extend to misinformation or decisional interference)
- **T11.** Propagation of sensor data to application providers: HomeSys may at some point share personal information of the HomeSys and Building users that is not relevant for a specific application to these applications (e.g. by using a broadcast data sharing system rather than a subscription based, or it may fail to enforce access control to regulate which sensor information propagates to which applications).
 - *Extent of impact-score*: **High** (Not controlling how data may propagate to the different application providers may give specific providers access to data it is not entitled to)
- **T12.** Propagation of personal data to third parties (e.g advertiser): HomeSys may at some point start selling or repurposing the collected data sets that consist of personal data of HomeSys and Building users (e.g., for analytics and predictive modeling).
 - *Extent of impact-score*: **Medium** (The data subject will have approved and made aware to this practice)
- **T13.** Propagation of personal data: High-volume data set may become public after a data leak or security incident (in HomeSys or in DBaaS provider).

- *Extent of impact-score: Medium* (Security issue with significant privacy implications)
- **T14. Aggregation** as HomeSys itself collects data of a single user too extensively or over too long periods of time.
 - *Extent of impact-score: Medium* (this is necessary for the applications to work correctly)
- **T15. Loss of deniability** Because of the sensor data collected by HomeSys, and the fact that some of these may be identifiable and attributable (e.g. pictures), the user may no longer have plausible deniability of their whereabouts or actions.
 - *Extent of impact-score: Medium* (the home environment is considered a personal space)
- **T16. Exposure:** An observer may figure out a particular home owner has a HomeSys installation, e.g. because the devices may be visible from the outside, or by sniffing wireless network traffic.
 - *Extent of impact-score: Low* (the fact that a person may be a HomeSys user in of its own does not convey much to an observer).

1.3. Expand privacy impact trees

We expand the privacy impact cases with a High Extent-score, and propagate this Extent downwards to the leaf nodes.

T2: Surveillance of HomeSys or Building users. This tree explores the possible outcome that an operator of HomeSys or an external application provider may single out a user of interest, and obtain access to large, accurate, perhaps real-time data sets of feeds. Figure 3 presents the corresponding tree.

It considers the possibility that surveillance capabilities (extensive, unchecked and unmotivated data access) is provided to the HomeSys operators in the first two branches. Then, it evaluates the possibility of providing too much access to data to applications and the lack of containment of this data within the applications, allowing them to propagate to a surveilling actor (the developer).

T3. Sensor data inaccuracy and HomeSys user misrepresentation. Figure 4 shows a privacy impact tree that systematically explores different possibilities of inaccuracy in the recorded sensor data, with particular attention to how this may lead to misrepresentation of the HomeSys users.

In the first branch, the sensor data itself is accurate but the attribution to the actual end-user is incorrect; for example, because the

Figure 3: T2. Privacy impact tree that explores the possibilities of a discriminatory or exclusionary outcome of HomeSys. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

Figure 4: T3. Privacy impact tree used to analyze the privacy impacts when inaccurate sensor is being collected.

home is shared by different people (e.g., an airbnb rental property), the data obtained for temporary guests may inadvertently be added to the profile of the homeowner. Alternatively, this could be the outcome of improper sensor and identity management, e.g. because a sensor is used in the home that was linked to a different user before, and was gifted, stolen, repurposed or sold to another user without removing the link to the original owner.

In the second and third branches, two specific possibilities of incorrect or inaccurate sensor data being recorded are presented: the sensor could malfunction (second branch), or it could be incorrectly calibrated (third branch).

A final option (fourth branch) expresses the data inaccuracy as an outcome of mishandling or wrongful installation of the sensors. The first sub-branch evaluates an adversarial case, i.e. it considers the situation in which a HomeSys user may deliberately try to tamper with the sensor data. This example shows that in privacy impact tree analysis (PITA), adversarial cases (security attacks or deliberate malicious or accidental user actions) remain of interest. However, these adversarial cases will never be represented as tree roots, but as intermediate nodes or leaves. The specific node (“Active, deliberate mishandling of sensors”) could in fact be a reference to a (security) attack tree that explores the security threats harming the integrity of the data (e.g., man-in-the-middle-attack, tampering, spoofing, etc.). The final sub-branch explores the possibility that inaccurate data is caused unintentionally; for example, when a temperature sensor is installed too closely to a door or window, it may misrepresent the actual room temperature.

As in the previous example, Extent- and Exposure-scores were determined and propagated. In this tree, the nodes depicted in gray contribute to the a posteriori impact of the system, i.e. these are the nodes and conditions that the HomeSys design contributes to and could manage or mitigate, in this case, by adopting more identity and sensor management controls (checking sensor identity and evaluating the link to its owner, or making sensor reuse technically infeasible without re-registration). In this tree, the a-priori nodes do not contribute to the overall privacy footprint.

T4. Lack of proactive communication towards Building users.

The possibility the HomeSys records personal information of users that are simply not aware of these data collection activities is real and impactful. Especially in open, shared environments (e.g, office buildings, apartment buildings,..) unregistered building users may be recorded without their awareness or consent. Figure 6 illustrates the possibilities.

A solution, unlikely to be present is that HomeSys would have to

Figure 5: T4. Privacy impact tree evaluating the consequences of lacking human oversight. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

actively identify users and then, based on whether these users have consented and been made aware, disregard data coming from users for which no consent and approval has been given. This is highly unlikely to have been implemented in HomeSys and technically challenging. Addressing this issue may require changing the technical and business goals of HomeSys.

T6. Loss of control, intervention or oversight upon malfunction. The main goal of HomeSys is to automate a number of home-related facilities, taking over activities that are currently conducted manually (e.g., operating or configuring the heating system, starting appliances such as washing machines and dishwashers). Yet, the situation in which any form of control or intervention of such activities would be entirely lacking could be considered detrimental to the HomeSys user and requires particular attention. For example, if the system malfunctions and the user is incapable of overriding the automated activities, it could lead to dissatisfaction, safety issues, etc.

Figure 6 presents a privacy impact tree that evaluates the implications when insufficient means to intervene or enact oversight have been foreseen in those parts of the system that perform automated-decision making.

The first branch focuses on the lack of intervention means offered to humans, i.e. neither a human HomeSys operator is sufficiently involved (they have not been foreseen such a role, or they are unreachable when the system malfunctions, e.g. due to network failure, or simply because of their work schedule), or the HomeSys user has not been provided with manual controls (e.g., configuration dashboards, a user app) to either override an automated decision in case of necessity (e.g., when being locked in or out of the home), or re-configure the system to prevent future malfunctioning of the automated decision-making.

The second branch considers the case in which these facilities are

Figure 6: T6. Privacy impact tree evaluating the consequences of lacking human oversight. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

available, but they themselves malfunction, due to insufficient testing, lack of resilience or availability, due to lack of performance (slow reaction time to mitigate urgent situations, e.g. when trying to close a valve in situations of water pipes bursting, etc.).

In applications that make impactful decisions (e.g., physical access control to the home, regulate costly operations such as heating systems, etc.) the lack of control is considered problematic, as the HomeSys user will be confronted with the outcomes of such decisions (house being burglarized, high energy bills) without having been capable of controlling these outcomes. Again, the nodes depicted in gray represent a-posteriori outcomes; in this case, the ability to provide means of intervention is entirely up to the system architect, and these risks contribute entirely to the privacy footprint of HomeSys.

T7: HomeSys user exclusion. Apart from increasing convenience, home automation brings a number of benefits to individuals and to society. For example, through smart heating, the operation of a heating system can be tuned more closely to meet demand, thus reducing heating costs. This also reduces the population-wide energy consumption and increases the overall sustainability, with beneficial effects to air quality, etc. If unchecked, systematically excluding specific users from these benefits would be considered unfair or problematic from a societal perspective, increasing the digital and social divide among users.

Figure 7 shows a privacy impact tree that evaluates the possibilities of an exclusionary outcome of HomeSys, i.e. a situation in which a person is not capable or allowed to access and benefit from the HomeSys services. The first branch of this tree evaluates the possibil-

Figure 7: T7. Privacy impact tree that explores the possibilities of a discriminatory or exclusionary outcome of HomeSys. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

ity of being excluded from using a relevant application by HomeSys itself. HomeSys applications only work when the necessary sensors and actuators have been installed in the home environment. In the first sub-branch, the situation is considered when these devices are not easily accessible, due to them being too specific, too costly or rare (limited in supply). The second sub-branch then considers the case in which the end user is insufficiently able to change the home environment, e.g. in a rental property in which the use and physical installation of sensors and actuators is explicitly prohibited in the rental contract. The second case considers the consequence of a typical gradual release strategy of new applications (or application updates). It is customary in a canary release strategy that new software is first only released to a subset of users for the purposes of gathering early feedback. However, depending on how this group of early testers or adopters is established, this could be construed as exclusionary, as it gives a limited group early access to the advantages of the new applications.

The second main branch considers the case in which a HomeSys user loses a degree of self-determination, for example because they are using a specific technology stack and therefore can no longer migrate to an alternative platform, due to lack of facilities for data extraction or data portability, or due to hardware incompatibility with other services (lock-in). This is a case in which the use of HomeSys technology itself has exclusionary outcomes on the end-user.

The third and final branch evaluates the possibility of the sensor data (i) being used for profiling of users, (ii) then these profiles being shared to third parties, and (iii) then these profiles being used for exclusionary purposes. For example, based on HomeSys data, the distinction could be made between users systematically working from home and users frequently not at home, and the shared outcomes could lead to specific users facing adjusted home insurance fees in consequence.

Each node in the tree of Figure 7 has additionally been labeled

with an Extent- and Exposure-score. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually by the analyst, whereas scores printed in italics were derived through upwards or downwards propagation. For example, it was determined that the likelihood (Exposure) of profile information deliberately being shared or sold to third parties is considered low (L), as this is not a current and integral part of the business model of HomeSys. In consequence, the entire third branch has been tagged less likely (upwards propagation of the Exposure-scores).

Finally, the nodes of this tree printed in gray are all highly specific to design decisions of the HomeSys system, i.e. in the a-priori situation, none of these branches would be applicable. Adopting the aggregation technique to evaluate the overall privacy footprint in the context of this tree shows us that an exclusionary outcome would be of medium Exposure due to the fact that some segments of the overall population would not be able to benefit from HomeSys services due to their housing context ('inability to change the home').

T8. Identity leakage to the storage provider. Figure 8 focuses on the different ways in which identity of the HomeSys users may be leaked to the third-party storage provider (the DBaaS provider), who is responsible for persistence and longer-term storage of the collected sensor data records in the Sensor DB.

In the most straightforward case (first branch), the identity could be included directly in the sensor data sets. For example, each sensor data record could include a username attribute that explicitly names the owner of the sensor from which the data has been collected (e.g., first name and family name). This case is considered unlikely, given that it requires extra enrichment steps in HomeSys, whereas the link between a HomeSys user and a specific sensor would be kept in the User DB.

Another possibility (second branch) is that the system uses indirect identifiers (quasi-identifiers). For example, the records could include an attribute that holds the unique sensor identifier, which at any given moment in time can be mapped one-to-one to a specific user. In that case, having access to this mapping between such quasi-identifiers and direct identifiers is another precondition. This could be either due to an identification scheme that leaks identity (e.g., the sensor identifiers are structured as 'userid-sensorid' concatenations) or because such information is accessible to the third party storage provider, e.g. the user database (User DB) has suffered a data leak, or a specific user may have written a review online about with details (e.g. log entries) about the specific sensor, which ties their identity in the review website to that specific device.

The third and fourth branches express two situations in which

the actual sensor data contain identifying information. In the third branch, this is the case because there are unique patterns or user fingerprints in the data, for example, the data reflects unique user behavior which can be tied to a single person. In the fourth branch, the situation is considered of more unstructured information such as pictures, video or audio that can still be used to convey identity. For example, the sensor data may include an image of the user (in case of a camera), or a unique discriminating characteristic of the user (e.g., a tattoo or iris). Another example is the presence of speech information (in case of microphone data) that can be used re-identify a person.

As in the above example, the privacy Extent-scores has been determined top-down (downwards propagation in the tree) and the Exposure-scores of the privacy impact has been set bottom-up (upwards propagation in the tree structures).

T11. Propagation of sensor data to application providers. Given that application providers actually deploy code that will operate within the HomeSys infrastructure, they may be well capable of propagating the sensor data to beyond the scope of the operational (e.g., to enact surveillance, as explored in T2). Figure 9 depicts the privacy impact tree for this potential case. This example depends on whether HomeSys will allow applications –that run in the HomeSys backend– will be accessible and connected to the outside world. Ideally, the applications are sandboxed (i.e., they run in a controlled environment with minimal permissions) so that propagation beyond their scope is not possible (second branch). In cases where this is impossible, e.g. because the application itself has back-end services, the communications must be monitored and metered (third branch). Fi-

Figure 8: T8. Privacy impact tree evaluating the possibility of identity leakage to the DBaaS provider. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

Figure 9: T11. Privacy impact tree evaluating the possibility of identity leakage to the DBaaS provider. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

nally, application code must be audited and tested before acceptance for eventual backdoors that may give cause to these propagations of sensor data to application providers.

1.4. Evaluate and propagate Exposure-scores.

In the Privacy Impact Tree Figures presented in the previous section, the Exposure assessment has already been indicated per tree leaf. For each three root, an overall Extent-score was indicated.

We now apply the mechanism of upwards propagation of the Exposure-scores toward the tree root, and downwards propagation of the Extent-score to all the intermediate nodes and leaves.

In each of the examples, we have annotated the propagated (deduced) value in *italics*.

The results can be seen in Figures 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16.

This completes the prioritization of the HomeSys privacy impact trees.

2. Mitigation phase.

2.1. Select a leaf node

In the mitigation phase, we systematically focus on the privacy impact trees with the highest Extent- and Exposure-scores. For HomeSys, based on the results presented above, these are the following three trees:

- **T4. Lack of proactive communication towards Building users.**

Here, the leaf “HomeSys does not actively identify users and thus can

Figure 10: T2. Privacy impact tree that explores the possibilities of a discriminatory or exclusionary outcome of HomeSys. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

Figure 11: T3. Privacy impact tree used to analyze the privacy impacts when inaccurate sensor is being collected, after Extent and Exposure propagation (in *italics*).

Figure 12: T4. Privacy impact tree evaluating the consequences of lacking human oversight, after Extent and Exposure propagation (in *italics*).

Figure 13: T6. Privacy impact tree evaluating the consequences of lacking human oversight, after Extent and Exposure propagation (in italics).

Figure 14: Privacy impact tree that explores the possibilities of a discriminatory or exclusionary outcome of HomeSys. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

Figure 15: T8. Privacy impact tree evaluating the possibility of identity leakage to the DBaaS provider, after Extent and Exposure propagation (in italics).

Figure 16: T11. Privacy impact tree evaluating the possibility of identity leakage to the DBaaS provider, after Extent and Exposure propagation (in italics).

not distinguish between registered (consenting/aware) and unregistered users (non-consenting/unaware)" is selected.

- **T6. Automated HomeSys application malfunctions.** Here, the leaf *"No controls offered to manually override the system"* is selected.
- **T8. DBaaS provider can identify HomeSys users in sensor data.** Here, the two leaves *"Sensor data contains patterns unique to a HomeSys user (fingerprints)"* and *"Unstructured sensor data itself contains identifying information"* are selected.

2.2. Mitigation

We introduce a number of mitigations in the respective privacy impact trees.

Figure 17 shows the result for the T4 privacy impact tree. We consider two complementary approaches: proactively informing the unregistered user and obtaining consent, or dynamically changing the data processing activities in functions of the specific user. Both approaches require a mechanism to differentiate between registered and unregistered users.

Figure 18 illustrates a specific mitigation to include a privacy dashboard and possibly a kill switch in cases of malfunction, in the context of the T6 privacy impact tree.

Finally, Figure 25 shows the introduction of encryption of sensor data before outsourcing this to the cloud provider as privacy mitigation.

Figure 17: T4. Privacy impact tree evaluating the consequences of lacking human oversight, after introducing some privacy mitigations (in gray, ovals).

Figure 18: T6. Privacy impact tree evaluating the consequences of insufficient intervention, adding a mitigation (in gray, oval shape).

Figure 19: T8. Privacy impact tree evaluating the possibility of identity leakage to the DBaaS provider, adding a mitigation (in gray, oval shape).

Calculating the privacy footprint score of HomeSys

We now illustrate how these outcomes can be aggregated in an expression of the overall HomeSys *privacy footprint*. For demonstration purposes, this is done at the basis of the High-impact trees detailed above.

We annotate for each tree node whether it is affected by the system and its design choices.

Table 2 summarizes the trees and compares the a-priori and a-posteriori risks. In the final row, it summarizes and aggregates these results into an expression of the overall privacy footprint of HomeSys.

The number printed between brackets counts the number of branches contributing to this Exposure-score.

Through comparing the a-priori situation to the a-posteriori situation, we can reason about the overall privacy footprint of the HomeSys application.

Similarly, we show the a-posteriori situation that takes into account the integrated mitigations.

Figure 20: T2. Privacy impact tree that explores the possibilities of a discriminatory or exclusionary outcome of HomeSys. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Figure 21: T3. Privacy impact tree used to analyze the privacy impacts when inaccurate sensor is being collected. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Figure 22: T4. Privacy impact tree evaluating the consequences of lacking human oversight, after propagation of Extent- and Exposure-scores. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Figure 23: T6. Privacy impact tree evaluating the consequences of lacking human oversight. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Figure 24: Privacy impact tree that explores the possibilities of a discriminatory or exclusionary outcome of HomeSys. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Figure 25: T8. Privacy impact tree evaluating the possibility of identity leakage to the DBaaS provider. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Figure 26: T11. Privacy impact tree evaluating the possibility of identity leakage to the DBaaS provider. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Privacy impact tree	<u>Extent</u>	A-priori	<u>Exposure</u> A- posteriori- without mitigations	A posteriori- mitigations
T2: Surveillance of HomeSys or Building users. (Figure 20)	H	M (1)	M (2)	M (2)
T3. Sensor data inaccuracy and HomeSys user misrepresentation. (Figure 21)	M	H (2)	H (2)	H (2)
T4. Lack of proactive communication towards Building users. (Figure 22)	H	o	H (1)	M (2)
T6. Loss of control, intervention or oversight upon malfunction. (Figure 23)	H	L (1)	H (1)	M (2)
T7: HomeSys user exclusion. (Figure 24)	H	M (1)	H (1)	H (1)
T8. Identity leakage to the storage provider. (Figure 25)	H	M (1)	H (2)	M (1)
T11. Propagation of sensor data to application providers. (Figure 26)	H	o	M (2)	M (2)
Privacy footprint $f(\text{HomeSys})$	H	o (2) L (1) M (3) H (2)	M (4) H (7)	M (9) H (4)

Table 2: Summary of the four privacy impact trees, summarizing impact and a-priori and the a-posteriori Exposure-scores (both with and without privacy mitigations). The bottom row aggregates the overall privacy footprint.

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